

A Digital Twin of a Battery Manufacturing Pilot Line

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This document provides the link giving access to our Digital Twin of the Battery Manufacturing Pilot Line of the Réseau du Stockage Electrochimique de l'Energie (RS2E) located in Amiens, France:

https://erc-artistic.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/digitaltwin/index.html

We release this Digital Twin today (June 17, 2022) embedded in a webpage. This Digital Twin takes the form of a serious game developed with the support of the Culture Scientifique of the Université de Picardie Jules Verne and empowered with the data acquired and digital representations developed in the ERC-funded ARTISTIC Project (www.erc-artistic.eu) led by Prof. Alejandro A. Franco (www.modeling-electrochemistry.com) at the Laboratoire de Réactivité et Chimie des Solides (LRCS, UMR CNRS 7314) (www.lrcs.u-picardie.fr/en/). By using the keyboard and mouse pad of your computer, you can navigate the Digital Twin and accomplish the mission indicated on the board at the beginning of the game: fabricating a lithium ion battery cell with target properties. You will be allowed to proceed further in the manufacturing process if you select the right parameters in each machine. Enjoy and good luck ! Full publication by us about this Digital Twin coming out soon !